

GAME-BASED LEARNING AS ASSESSMENT TOOL
IN MATHEMATICS EDUCATION

A Research
Presented to
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BAGUIO CENTRAL UNIVERSITY
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Master of Arts in Mathematics

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THE PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Game-based learning (GBL) is one of the modern trends in education in the 21st century. Since 2019, the number of studies relating to game-based learning has increased (Hui & Mahmud, 2023). Effective manipulatives and games play a crucial role in promoting mathematical understanding. They support students in building, reinforcing and connecting varied representations of mathematical concepts (Debrenti, 2024). GBL is a teaching technique which allows the cognitive sequence to be reversed by introducing game elements in problem solving. Game Based Learning (GBL) is, therefore, a lock pick to interest the class, capture students' attention and allow them to understand the concepts of Math and its procedures in an intuitive way (Scientix, 2023).

Further, Orbon and Sapin (2022) mentioned in their study that while students are having fun, educational games encourage them to come up with original ideas and push them to learn more quickly. Their confidence is increased by the conversations students have with one another to provide a lasting learning effect. Aside from, according to Samortin (2023), it is recommended that teachers should employ a game-based approach and other strategies for the vocabulary learning process; however, teachers should plan and choose some appropriate teaching strategies suited to the level of the students, and the availability of the materials as well.

Meanwhile, in Baguio City, Adonis Togana, a Math Teacher of Joaquin Smith National High School, devised a solution to keep his student's attention and let them have better understanding on the lessons while having fun. The Math teacher incorporate games in his lessons and the students actively participate (Calayan, 2024). On the other hand, according to Ayeras, Colas, and Regua (2023) from University of the Cordilleras, due to Mathematics' abstract nature and reliance on symbolic representations, it can be intimidating for many students. This challenge is magnified for students with special needs who might struggle to learn through conventional teaching methods that largely focus on verbal and visual communication.

The reasons of the researcher for undertaking this study are to identify the commonly used game-based learning as assessment tool in Mathematics Education and its frequency of usage.

Aside from, the study opts to determine the level of effect, together with the constraints of game-based learning as assessment tool in Mathematics Education. There is a need to conduct this study because this can help schools and teachers especially mathematics teachers to have ideas in teaching the subject matter. In addition, the output of this research will help future educators and even students who struggles in Mathematics as this provides context in a particular type of teaching and learning approach. Other students didn't seem to appreciate Mathematics even when teachers emphasize the applications and relevance of it in real-life; because, students didn't enjoy learning the subject, since they consider it as a boring subject with no thrill. Overall, the research is beneficial to schools, teachers, students, and future researchers.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework of the Study

The following theories supported the study entitled Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education. This study aims to identify the commonly used game-based learning, its frequency of usage, level of effect, and the constraints in using game-based learning.

Game theory is a mathematical concept that aims to predict outcomes and solutions to an issue in which parties with conflicting, overlapping or mixed interests interact (Willmer, 2022). The game encourages creativity and motivation by posing challenges and problems that students must solve using their imagination (Gamelearn Team, 2015). It provides frameworks to analyze how players make strategic decisions in various scenarios where the outcome depends on the actions of others (COMAP, 2024). The research undertaking focuses on the utilization of games on Mathematics Education; wherein, it is related to the Game theory as they both aims to encourage participation against students through its engaging and interesting nature.

Flow theory can be adopted for measuring user experience and analyzing the quality of serious game designs. In addition, flow seems to have a positive influence on performance enhancement, learning and engagement (Perttula et. al., 2017). The first construct of flow theory includes clear goals and immediate feedback. The implementation of this construct through learning experience design allows the learner to know what is expected of them and receive instantaneous assessment on their performance (Vann & Tawfik, n.d.). In connection with the research paper, it also opts to identify if game-based learning can positively affect the academic performance and classroom participation of the students.

Constructivism as a theory can be successful in the teaching and educational process as students learn experientially rather than just from the textbook. Students are encouraged to use their critical thinking, deductive reasoning, and analytical abilities to articulate their thoughts and come up with solutions (Ravi, 2024). Constructivist theory is the concept of “learning by doing” and this can be implemented in this digital era through game-based learning where individual students can learn themselves how to solve problems and make decisions through games. The interactive tasks are also customizable (WordPress, n.d.). Further, the study, game-based learning is an example of constructivism since it allows children to learn through psychomotor.

The aforementioned theories and concepts helped shape the study. These theories were served as a guide in developing the study as it helped the researcher to further understand her study.

Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 presents the schematic diagram of the study showing the relationships of the variables.

The input contains the title, Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education. The process involves the quantitative design, descriptive and inferential method, questionnaire, statistical treatment of data, and analysis and interpretation of data. The output shall be a proposed activity particularly, recommendations in using game-based learning as assessment tool.

Figure 1: Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

The study shall focus on determining the effectiveness of Game-based Learning as Assessment tool in Mathematics Education. Specifically, the study seeks answers to the following queries:

1. What is the commonly used Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education?
2. What is the frequency of Usage of Game-Based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education?
3. What is the level of effect of Game-Based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education?
4. What are the constraints in Using Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education?

Research Assumptions/Hypotheses

The study hypothesizes the following:

1. The commonly used Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education is Puzzles.
2. The frequency of usage of Game-Based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education is Sometimes.
3. The level of effect of Game-Based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education is Moderate Effect.
4. The constraints in using Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education are Lack of time and Lack of Appropriate Games.

Chapter 2

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the design and methodology which will be utilized by the researcher in conducting the study. It contains the research design, locale and population of the study, data gathering instrument, reliability and validity of the study, data gathering procedure, treatment of data, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The study will employ descriptive research design. According to Kowalczyk (2022), descriptive research seeks to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon by collecting data through surveys, observations, or questionnaires.

The study shall be using quantitative method. Quantitative research is a structured way of collecting and analyzing data from various sources. Its purpose is to quantify the problem and understand its extent, seeking results that someone can project to a larger population (Fleetwood, 2024). Lastly, a questionnaire shall be used to gather the responses from respondents.

Locale and Population of the Study

The study will be conducted at Baguio Central University, Bonifacio, Baguio City. Baguio Central University was chosen as a local of the study because that is where the researcher is currently enrolled for Graduate School.

The respondents shall be the teachers who are currently taking Master of Arts in Mathematics since the study focuses on how teachers apply game-based learning as assessment tool in Mathematics Education. Aside from, the researcher shall use simple random sampling and there shall be 30 respondents.

Data gathering Instrument

The researcher will use adapted questionnaire from the study of Rocha et. al. and self-made questionnaire in gathering data in a form of drop-down questions. Further, gathering data from teachers who are enrolled in Master of Arts in Mathematics will be personally conducted by the researcher.

The questionnaire shall contain the following parts: Part 1 will consist drop-down questions regarding the commonly used game-based learning as assessment tool. Part 2 will contain

questions on the frequency of usage of game-based learning, while part 3 will present questions on its level of effect. Lastly, part 4 will contain the constraints in using game-based learning.

Reliability and Validity of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument will be administered to ten (10) English teachers who are pursuing Masters of Arts in English in Baguio Central University and shall employ Cronbach's Alpha by comparing the amount of shared variance or covariance, among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance Cronbach's alpha is a measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability (UCLA, 2024). The formula is as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{N\underline{c}}{\underline{v} + (N - 1)\underline{c}}$$

Where:

N = number of items

c = average covariance between item – pairs

v = average variance

Validity shall be established by having the questionnaire be checked for congruency through the Validity Evaluation Form (BCU Research Manual) by the panel of examiners.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the study, the researcher will secure permission to float her questionnaire from the Dean of the Graduate School of Baguio Central University (BCU). The researcher shall be seeking similar permission from office head. Then, the researcher shall personally administer the questionnaire to the intended respondents.

Treatment of Data

The questionnaire to be accomplished will be retrieved, tallied, tabulated, and treated accordingly. The data shall be treated to frequency, weighted mean, t-test, and ranking.

Part 1 shall use tick box questionnaire to identify the commonly used Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education.

To determine the weighted mean, the researcher shall make use of the 4-point scale to measure the respondent's responses to the survey. The following are the scales to be used in the study:

Part 2. Frequency of Usage of Game-Based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education

Value	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent	Symbol
4	3.25-4.00	Always	A
3	2.50-3.24	Sometimes	SO
2	1.75-2.49	Rare	R
1	1.00-1.74	Never	N

Part 3. Level of Effect of Game-Based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education

Value	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent	Symbol
4	3.25-4.00	High Effect	HE
3	2.50-3.24	Moderate Effect	ME
2	1.75-2.49	Low Effect	LE
1	1.00-1.74	Slight Effect	SE

Part 3. Constraints in Using Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education

Value	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent	Symbol
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA
3	2.50-3.24	Agree	A
2	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD

Ethical Considerations

Before conducting the study, the researcher shall undertake the following procedures to ensure ethical considerations in the conduct of research:

The researcher shall secure first a written permission to float the researcher's instrument from the school authorities of the intended respondents of the study;

A letter accompanying the research instrument will be given to the target respondents indicating among others; to wit: (1) the respondents' identity will not be divulged in the current study in compliance to the provision of the Data Privacy Act Law; (2) all information and data from the respondents of the study will be held in strict confidentiality; when the respondents answers the survey instrument, that means they agreed to participate in the study as respondents; (3) the responses in the instrument will be presented in aggregate form and not as individual perceptions; and (4) the research will be conducted primarily for academic requirement only.

The researcher guarantees that all materials that was used in this study were properly cited and any information gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

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Appendix A

Letter to the Respondents

Dear Respondents,

The undersigned, pursuing Master of Arts in Mathematics, is conducting a research titled Game-Based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education. The purpose of the study is to look into the commonly used game-based learning as assessment tool in Mathematics by teachers, its effectiveness, and the constraints in using game-based learning. In this regard, you are kindly requested to give your responses for each question to the best of your knowledge. Your answers shall be treated in strict confidentiality and rest assured to be used for academic purposes only.

Sincerely,

Dominijoyz A. Culop

Researcher

QUESTIONNAIRE

Name (optional): _____

Course: _____

Part I: What is the commonly used Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education?

Direction: Please put a tick in the box before the type/s of game-based learning that you commonly used in teaching Mathematics.

Flash Card-Type Games

Puzzles

Simulation Games

Strategy Games

Interactives

Reality Testing Games

Quiz Games

If others, please specify:

Part II: What is the usage frequency of Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education?

Direction: Please rate the usage frequency of game-based learning during diagnostic assessment, formative assessment, and summative assessment.

A – Always

S – Sometimes

R – Rare

N - Never

	Diagnostic Assessment				Formative Assessment				Summative Assessment			
	A	S	R	N	A	S	R	N	A	S	R	N
Flash-card Type Games												
Simulation Games												
Interactives												
Quiz Games												
Puzzles												
Strategy Games												
Reality Testing Games												
If others, please specify:												

Part III. What is the level of effects of Game-Based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education?

Direction: Please rate the effects of game-based learning that you commonly used in teaching Mathematics among learners.

HE – High Effect ME – Moderate Effect SE- Slight Effect LE – Low Effect

Effects of Game-Based Learning	HE	ME	SE	LE
1. Students' Learning Goal Achievements				
2. Interaction Between Students				
3. Students' Motivation				
4. Enhanced Memory and Retention				
5. Improved Problem-Solving Skills				
6. Active Participation				
7. Development of Critical Thinking Skills				
8. Foster Creativity				

Part III: What are the constraints in using Game-based Learning as Assessment Tool in Mathematics Education?

Direction: Please rate the constraints in using game-based learning that you've encountered in teaching Mathematics.

SA – Strongly Agree A- Agree D- Disagree SD- Strongly Disagree

Constraints	SA	A	D	SD
1. Lack of Time				
2. Lack of Appropriate Games				
3. Lack of Knowledge (how to use various types of game-based learning, etc.)				
4. Lack of Resources				
5. Does not Apply to My Case				
6. Lack of Opportunity				
7. Students are not Interested				

Source: Rocha, M., Tangney, B., Dondio, P. (2018). *Play and Learn: Teachers' Perceptions About Classroom Video Games*. <https://www.researchgate.net>

